

IMPACT OF GENDER ENROLMENT IN HOME ECONOMICS IN HIGHER INSTITUTIONS: A CASE STUDY OF UNIVERSITY OF JOS, PLATEAU STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract

Gender is an overlooked issue in Nigerian system of education which to a large extent needs to be addressed in order to ensure gender equality in enrolment in all fields of study. To this end, this study was conducted to determine the impact of gender enrolment in Home Economics, using University of Jos as a case study. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of study consisted of 10,000 students from the Faculty of Education. A sample of 385 students was used for the study. A simple random sampling technique was used in selecting the 385 students made up of 185 male students and 200 female students. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire, made up of 32 items. Three research questions and three null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The research questions were analyzed using mean and standard deviation while the null hypotheses were tested using t-test statistical tool at 0.05 level of significance. Some findings of the study revealed that the society generally sees Home Economics as a female based course; not a marketable course and that services in the area are more beneficial to females. Some of the impacts of gender enrolment in Home Economics when it is female dominated as found by the study leads to shortage of manpower in other related fields, barrier to long-run economic development and gender biasness in the economy. Some misperceptions about Home Economics as revealed by the findings of this study can be tackled through proper enlightenment and organizing workshops and seminars to address the importance of male involvement in the profession. The study recommends that

Home Economics should be made a compulsory elective course to all students irrespective of their fields of study and the society should change their perception on the jobs and activities that are for male and females in the home and society.

Keywords: Gender, Enrolment, Home Economics, Higher institution, Society.

Introduction

Home economics is the education for living. It is the study of all that relate to home and family. It is the area of study that provides the necessary knowledge guiding and assisting human being to be able to attain a more self-reliance and fulfilled life. (Neequaye, Darkwa, & Amu,.2014). Home economics deals with all aspects of family living, drawing knowledge from many disciplines such as Biology, Physics, Social Science, Humanities and Arts, and unifying the knowledge drawn to teach people how to do the followings: Determine the needs of individuals and families and become responsible and effective members of family and community through effective home making and gainful employment (Anyakoha, 2015).

Eze (2001) pointed out that Home Economics is capable of preparing youths and adults for entry into various areas in Home Economics occupations. This shows that as a vocational subject, Home Economics contributes to manpower development by equipping individuals with reliable occupational skills, which lead to self-reliance. According to Ajayi, K., & Buessing, M. (2013). Home Economics can also help individuals (male and female) acquire basic skills needed for gainful employment and family living. It could also be known that Home Economics as a field of study does not exclude gender, age or any other classification. Home Economics is a very important subject in the University Curriculum. The program has many career opportunities, for the University graduates. It also prepares individual for happy family life. Both male and female students study the subject at the University.

Teaching people about the importance of Home economics is very necessary. There should be enlightenment campaigns through seminars and mass media about the importance of Home Economics and the career opportunities that subject provides. Eze (2001) recommended that parents should encourage their sons and daughters to develop interest and select Home Economics as a subject of study in schools; that there should be no mark sex discrimination in the activities and games which boys and girls are allowed to

participate at home: that parents should encourage their sons to choose Home Economics and related discipline; that careers in Home Economics are attractive and highly remunerated; that Home Economics teachers should not only teach their subject but also guidance counsellors to their students especially boys; that there should be emphasis on the provision of teaching facilities and career education that will help to attract boys and girls to study Home Economics. Ovule (2002) recommended the excursion or field trips as method of teaching Home Economics in all levels of education.

In Nigeria, Home Economics is taught as a compulsory subject for all primary pupils and junior secondary. Home Economics is one of the most popular optional subjects. More recently, home economics has been introduced at the elementary- school level and is taught in some general upper-secondary schools (Venäläinen, 2015). At the secondary-school level, home economics is taught mainly in vocational upper-secondary schools that have home economics-related training programmes in catering, hospitality services and domestic services. In universities, home economics science can be studied as a major at the bachelor's, master's and doctoral levels.

In basic education, the main objective of home economics education is to develop pupils' skills in cooperation, information acquisition and the practical work necessary to manage daily living. Topics taught include family and living together, nutrition and food culture, the consumer and changing society and the home and the environment. (Adinkrah, M. 2012). The aim of the subject is to teach general life skills for personal growth and development (Finnish National Board of Education, 2004). Promoting gender equality is one of the goals of home economics education (FNBE, 2004). However, a recent national assessment of home economics learning outcomes (Venäläinen, 2015) identifies significant differences in boy and girls' learning outcomes. Similarly, Anttila (2015) warns of the risk of taking for granted the expected promotion of gender equality by the common home economics education for boys and girls. Given that the general curriculum for basic education (FNBE, 2014) to be implemented in 2016 encourages the enabling of individual learning paths free from predominant gender positions, it is essential to consider how gender is reconstructed and discussed in home economics education.

Gender has been recognized as an overlooked issue in Nigerian teacher education that should be given more attention if gender equality is to be taken seriously. To illustrate the controversies in the Nigerian debate around gender and education, Lahelma (2011) gives examples of teachers and teacher

educators who suggest that gender is not a problem in schools but, in the same breath, expressed concerns about lack of interest among boys in Home Economics discipline. Therefore, a more gender-awareness approach is needed to advance gender equality in seemingly gender-neutral basic education in Nigeria. (Lahelma, 2011, 2014).

Home economics and its multiple content areas (e.g. food and nutrition, consumer issues, family studies, sustainable living) are understood and emphasized in different contexts in various ways (McGregor, 2011; Wahlen, Posti-Ahokas, and Collins, 2009). In the school subject of home economics, gender may be more visible and determinative of pupils' participation and roles than in other subjects. In both Ghana and Finland, home economics has a relatively strong position at different levels of education. In both contexts, gender has been defined as a critical yet overlooked issue in home economics education (Amu and Edjah, Anttila, Leskinen, Posti-Ahokas, and Janhonen-Abuquah, 2015). In Nigeria, gender inequality is recognized as a critical societal problem and discussed in relation to education policy, including setting targets for equal access and enrolment for male and female students. In addition, demand to meet the Millennium Development Goals focused on eliminating gender discrimination and inequalities in access and achievement at all levels of education requires attention to the subject of home economics, as it is a heavily female-dominated field of study across the educational system. (Agyare, 2013). In Finland, education policies and the national Curriculum increasingly emphasize the importance of replacing the prevailing gender-neutral rhetoric of current education policies and practices with gender awareness to advance gender equality (FNBE, 2014).

Graduating from Home Economics education, particularly at the basic education level, has been widely considered gender neutral (Turkki, 2011). However, the growing gender awareness promoted through research, policy and curricula has resulted in an increasing focus among home economists on gender-related problems within their field (Amu & Edjah, Anttila et al., 2015; Turkki, 2011). It is against this background that this study was intended to determine the impact of gender enrolment in Home Economics, using University of Jos as a case study.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the impact of gender in home economics enrolment in higher institution, University of Jos. Specifically the

study determined to find out the:

1. Causes of gender enrolment of home economics in university of Jos
2. Impact of gender in the enrolment of Home Economics in University of Jos.
3. Strategies to tackle gender enrolment of Home Economics education in University of Jos.

Research Questions

The study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the causes of gender enrolment of Home Economics in University of Jos?
2. What is the impact of gender enrolment of Home Economics education in University of Jos?
3. What are the strategies that can be used to tackle gender enrolment of Home Economics education in University of Jos.

Research Hypotheses

The study was guided by the following null hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the mean response of male and female students in the causes of gender enrolment of Home Economics in University of Jos.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean response of male and female students the impact of gender enrolment of Home Economics in University of Jos.
3. There is no significant difference between the mean response of male and female students the strategies that can be used to tackle gender enrolment of Home Economics education in University of Jos.

Methodology

The study employed descriptive survey research design where by a group of people or items are studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few people or items considered to be representative of the entire group (Akuezuiro & Agu, 2003). The area of the study was University of Jos, Department of Science and Technology Education, Plateau State of Nigeria.

Population for the Study

The population of study consisted of 10,000 students from the Faculty of Education, University of Jos. The Yamane formula was used to determine the sample size which stood at 385 students.

Sample for the Study

A simple random sampling technique was used in selecting 385 students made up of 185 male students and 200 female students. Altogether the sample size for the study was 385 respondents.

Instrument for the Study

A 28-item questionnaire was used to collect data. It was constructed by the researcher, based on literature reviewed. The items were treated on a four-point scale. Respondents were required to tick the option which best described their views on the items. The four-point scale treated the items as follows:

Strongly Agree (SA)	-	4 points
Agree (A)	-	3 points
Disagree (D)	-	2 points
Strongly Disagree (SD)	-	1 point

Three experts in the field of Home Economics Education validated the instrument in terms of face and content validation. In order to obtain a reliable instrument, the validated copy was trial-tested on 30 respondents from the Department of Home Economics, Modibbo Adama University of Technology, Yola, Adamawa State, North-East Nigeria. The test re-test method was used to establish the reliability of the instrument, using a correlational statistic of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (ρ). The Pearson (ρ) was found to be 0.77.

The administration of the questionnaire to the respondents and the retrieval of the filled questionnaire lasted for five days. At the end of the exercise, a total of 385 valid copies of the questionnaire were realized indicating 100% retrieval. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25 was used to analyze the research questions and to test the hypotheses. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested using t-test at 0.05 level of significance.

To effect decision, a mean of means score (\bar{x}) of 2.50 and above was considered “agree” and a mean of means score of less than 2.50 was considered “disagree”. The decision rule for the t-test analysis was: accept the null hypothesis if the calculated p-value exceeds the alpha value of 0.05; otherwise do not reject the null hypothesis if the p-value of the test statistic is less than the alpha value of 0.05 (Nworgu, 2006).

Presentation of Results

This is done based on the research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question One

What are the causes of gender in Home Economics Enrolment in University of Jos?

Table 1 shows the data that answered this research question. Mean and Standard Deviation of Male and Female Students on the Causes of Gender Stereotype in Home Economics Enrolment in University of Jos, Plateau State

S/N	Item	\bar{X}_1	$\hat{\sigma}_1$	\bar{X}_2	$\hat{\sigma}_2$	\bar{X}_T	Remark
1.	It's seen as a female based course.	3.37	0.50	2.83	0.77	3.09	A
2.	Lecturers in field of study are females.	3.21	0.47	3.05	1.12	3.13	A
3.	It is not a marketable course.	3.05	0.54	3.10	0.85	3.08	A
4.	Females are enrolled more than males.	3.22	0.93	2.91	0.96	3.06	A
5.	Parents influence on career choice.	2.90	0.86	3.31	0.70	3.11	A
6.	Lack of understanding of the course.	2.78	1.07	2.84	1.03	2.81	A
7.	Services in the area are more beneficial to Females.	3.02	1.02	3.20	0.87	3.11	A
8.	The course deals with domestic affairs.	3.00	1.06	2.90	1.11	2.95	A
9.	Low level of awareness of the course.	2.90	0.98	3.15	0.95	3.03	A
10.	I will be laughed at as male studying Home Economics	2.73	1.02	2.79	1.17	2.76	A

The data showed in table 1 above indicated that the mean scores of male students range between 2.73 and 3.37 with their standard deviation ranging between 0.47 and 1.07. The mean scores of female students range between 2.79 to 3.31 with their standard deviation ranging between 0.70 and 1.17 which means respondents' views do not differ significantly. However, the values of mean of means of the items as rated by male and female students range between 2.76 and 3.13. This revealed that all the items were agreed by the respondents as

the causes of gender stereotype in the enrolment of Home Economics in University of Jos, Plateau State.

Research Question Two

What is the impact of gender enrolment of Home Economics education in University of Jos?

Table 2 shows the data that answered this research question.

Mean and Standard Deviation of Male and Female Student son the Impact of Gender Enrolment in Home Economics University of Jos, Plateau State

S/N	Item	\bar{X}_1	$\partial_1 \bar{X}_2$	$\partial_2 \bar{X}_T$	Remark			
1.	Shortage of manpower in hotel management.		3.21	0.65	2.96	0.70	3.08	A
2.	Barrier to long-run economic development.		3.09	0.63	3.21	1.02	3.15	A
3.	Clash of perceptions between couples as regards home management.		1.97	0.70	2.24	0.74	2.11	D
4.	Promote gender biasness in the economy.		2.99	0.88	2.78	1.24	2.88	A
5.	Result to shortage of male graduates in the of Home Economics.		2.95	0.76	3.30	0.69	3.13	A
6.	Increase the number of males' joblessness.		2.93	0.93	3.05	1.10	2.99	A
7.	Rate of new discovery in the Home Economics is reduced.		2.94	0.98	3.35	0.82	3.15	A
8.	Home Economics will be seen as inferior to other field of studies thus funding it will be prioritize by Government.	3.06	0.97	3.06	0.96	3.06		A

The data showed in table 2 above revealed that the mean scores of male students range between 1.97 and 3.21 with their standard deviation ranging between 0.63 and 0.98. The mean scores of female students range between 2.24 to 3.35 with their standard deviation ranging between 0.69 and 1.24 which means respondents' views do not differ significantly. However, the values of mean of means of the items as rated by male and female students range between 2.11 and 3.15. The table further revealed that with exception to item 11 which was disagreed all other items were agreed by the respondents as the impact of gender stereotype in the enrolment of Home Economics in University of Jos, Plateau State.

Research Question Three

What are the strategies that can be used to tackle gender stereotype in the enrolment of Home Economics education in University of Jos?

Table 3 shows the data that answered this research question.

Mean and Standard Deviation on the Strategies to Tackle Gender enrolment in Home Economics in University of Jos, Plateau State

S/N	Item	X_1	$\hat{\sigma}_1 X_2$	$\hat{\sigma}_2 X_T$	Remark				
1.	Exposing male gender to household chores at early age.	3.21	0.65	2.90	0.74	3.05	A		
2.	Organizing workshops and seminars to brainstorm on the importance of gender equality in Home Economics.	3.03	0.78	3.24	1.01	3.14	A		
3.	Ensuring a regular public awareness about Home Economics via TV/Radio stations.	2.93	0.81	3.01	0.91	2.97	A		
4.	Giving both female and male gender equal Opportunity in career choice.	3.14	0.95	2.71	1.20	2.92	A		
5.	Putting in place a career unit in schools for proper orientation of students on the importance of each course of study.	2.92	0.82	3.35	0.71	3.14	A		
6.	Organizing field trips by schools to visit areas dominated by men in Home Economics.	2.84	1.06	2.94	1.09	2.89	A		
7.	Having an unbiased Home Economics curriculum from curriculum planners.	2.85	1.09	3.28	0.89	3.07	A		
8.	Adopting relevant methods in teaching Home Economics to encourage the few male students in the field to avoid the issue of change of course.	2.95	1.14	2.99	1.07	2.97	A		
9.	frequent sensitization of the public on the job opportunities in Home Economics.	3.01	0.82	3.24	0.98	3.13	A		
10.	having text books void of gender discrimination.	2.84	0.87	2.90	1.23	2.87	A		

The data showed in table 3 above revealed that the mean scores of male students range between 2.84 and 3.21 with their standard deviation ranging between 0.65 and 1.14. The mean scores of female students range between 2.90 to 3.35 with their standard deviation ranging between 0.71 and 1.23 which means respondents' views do not differ significantly. However, the values of mean of means of the items as rated by male and female students range between 2.87 and 3.14. The table further revealed that all the items were agreed by the respondents as the strategies that can be used to tackle gender stereotype in the enrolment of Home Economics education in University of Jos.

Testing of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were stated and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean response of male and female students the causes of gender stereotype in the enrolment of Home Economics in University of Jos.

This hypothesis was tested using t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The results were presented in table 4 below.

Table 4: t-test of Difference between Male and Female Students on the Causes of Gender Enrolment of Home Economics in University of Jos, Plateau State

Respondent	N	Mean	Mean Diff.	Std. Dev.	p-value	Decision
Male Students	185	3.018		0.845		
			0.01		0.908	NS
Female Students	200	3.008		0.953		

As presented in table 4 the means of male and female students stood at 3.018 and 3.008 and the mean difference stood at 0.01. Also, the standard deviations of the male and female students stood at 0.845 and 0.953 respectively. The table also revealed that the p-value obtained was 0.908. This indicated that the p-value was greater than the alpha at 0.05 level of significance i.e., $p > 0.05$. Therefore, there was no significant difference between the mean response of male and female students on the causes of gender stereotype in the enrolment of Home Economics in University of Jos. The null hypothesis was accepted.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean response of male and female students the impact of gender stereotype in the enrolment of Home Economics in University of Jos.

This hypothesis was tested using t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The results were presented in table 5 below.

Table 5: t-test of Difference between Male and Female Students on the Impact of Gender Enrolment of Home Economics in University of Jos, Plateau State

Respondent	N	Mean	Mean Diff.	Std. Dev.	p-value	Decision
Male Students	185	2.893		0.813		
			0.097		0.607	NS
Female Students	200	2.990		0.909		

As presented in table 5 the means of male and female students stood at 2.893 and 2.990 and the mean difference stood at 0.097. Also, the standard deviations of the male and female students stood at 0.813 and 0.909 respectively. The table also revealed that the p-value obtained was 0.607. This indicated that the p-value was greater than the alpha at 0.05 level of significance i.e., $p > 0.05$. Therefore, there was no significant difference between the mean response of male and female students on the impact of gender stereotype in the enrolment of Home Economics in University of Jos. The null hypothesis was accepted.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between the mean response of male and female students the strategies that can be used to tackle gender stereotype in the enrolment of Home Economics education in University of Jos.

This hypothesis was tested using t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The results were presented in table 6 below.

Table 6: t-test of Difference between Male and Female Students on the Strategies to Tackle Gender Enrolment of Home Economics in University of Jos, Plateau State

Respondent	N	Mean	Mean Diff.	Std. Dev.	p-value	Decision
Male Students	185	2.972		0.899		
			0.084		0.291	NS
Female Students	200	3.056		0.983		

As presented in table 6 the means of male and female students stood at 2.972 and 3.056 and the mean difference stood at 0.084. Also, the standard deviations of the male and female students stood at 0.127 and 0.209 respectively. The table also revealed that the p-value obtained was 0.291. This indicated that the p-value was greater than the alpha at 0.05 level of significance i.e., $p > 0.05$. Therefore, there was no significant difference between the mean response of male and female students on the strategies to tackle gender stereotype in the enrolment of Home Economics in University of Jos. The null hypothesis was accepted.

Discussion of Findings

Findings based on research question one as presented in table 1 showed that the respondents agreed with the following as the causes of gender stereotype in the enrolment of Home Economics among others: it is seen as a female based course, it is not a marketable course, lecturers in field of study are females, parents influence on career choice, lack of understanding of the course, services in the area are more beneficial to females. It was also found out that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female students on the causes of gender stereotype in the enrolment of Home Economics in University of Jos. These findings are in support with the findings of some researchers on the same issue. For instance, Avute (2001) found that enrolment in Home Economics is female dominated and had to recommend that parents should encourage male and female genders to choose Home Economics as a field of study. Lahelma (2011) also confirmed that lack of understanding on the opportunities home economics offer remains one of the reasons male gender do not have interest in getting enrolled in Home Economics discipline. Therefore, a more gender-awareness approach is needed to advance gender equality in seemingly gender-neutral basic education in Nigeria.

Findings based on research question two as indicated in table 2 revealed that shortage and barrier to long-run economic development, gender biasness in the economy, shortage of male graduates in the of Home Economics among others. Also, there was no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female students on the impact of gender stereotype in the enrolment of Home Economics in University of Jos, these findings revealed that gender inequality in the enrolment of Home Economics hampers the economic development of a nation. Thus, demand to meet the Millennium Development

Goals focused on eliminating gender discrimination and inequalities in access and achievement at all levels of education requires attention to the subject of Home Economics, as it is a heavily female-dominated field of study across the educational system. Buttressing this, education policies and the national curriculum increasingly emphasize the importance of replacing the prevailing gender-neutral rhetoric of current education policies and practices with gender awareness to advance gender equality (FNBE, 2014).

Findings based on research question three as presented in table 3 showed that the respondents agreed with the following as the strategies to tackle gender stereotype in the enrolment of Home Economics among others: exposing male gender to household chores at early age, organizing workshops and seminars to brainstorm on the importance of gender equality in Home Economics, ensuring a regular public awareness about Home Economics via TV/Radio stations among others. This implies that gender equality in the enrolment of Home Economics is achievable when the society is fully sensitized about the diverse opportunities the course offers irrespective of one's gender. It is in this light that opined that a more gender-awareness approach is needed to advance gender equality in seemingly gender-neutral basic education in Nigeria (Lahelma, 2011 and 2014).

Conclusion

From the result of the investigation, it was established that there is poor enrolment of home economics in university of Jos especially among the male counterparts. This could be as a result of so many factors which include; parents influence on the career choice of their children, poverty and illiteracy levels of the parents. All these in turn have so many negative effects on the development of individual, families, society and the nation at large.

Recommendations

- organizing enlightenment programmes for the general public on home economics education is one of the strategies for correcting the misconception on the subject.
- Home Economics should be made a compulsory elective course to all students irrespective of their fields of study.
- society should change their perception on the jobs and activities that are for male and females in the home and society.

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